

Energy Revenue Tracking and Renewable Transition (E-R2T2)

A proposal to the Philippine Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (PH-EITI)

By:

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Abstract:

This is a plan to use data to estimate government earnings from fossil fuel firms and switch to renewable energy, with an emphasis on giving underserved communities' access to energy. Strong data analysis, planning for renewable energy, public accessibility, community empowerment, and avoidance of conflicts of interest are some of the main components. Establishing a task force, working with stakeholders, creating a data management system, looking at revenue streams, creating a transition plan, developing a public online platform, putting renewable energy projects into action, monitoring and assessing the initiative's effects are all part of the implementation process. Transparency, accountability, sustainable development, innovation and investment, empowerment, and dispute resolution are among the main advantages. Citizens, customers, the environment, businesses, financiers and investors, the government and public institutions, and academics are among the gainers. The adoption of renewable energy sources, energy efficiency, social impact, governance and transparency, and economic impact all have associated hypotheses. The formulation of the energy transition plan, research, data collecting, proposal review and approval, implementation and monitoring, project planning and resource allocation, project assessment and reporting are all included in the project timeline.

1. Objective:

Utilize data to assess government earnings from fossil fuel companies and transition to renewable energy while prioritizing untapped communities without access to energy grids. This proposal uses existing theories and published works of individuals and institutions to serve as foundations of arguments.

2. Key Features:

- a. **Data Analysis:** Establish a robust system for tracking and analysing revenue generated by fossil fuel companies, ensuring transparency and accuracy.
- b. **Renewable Energy Planning:** Conduct in-depth research and analysis to develop a comprehensive roadmap for transitioning to renewable energy sources.
- c. **Public Accessibility:** Make all findings and data publicly available through an accessible online platform, empowering citizens and stakeholders to understand the government's earnings and renewable energy progress.
- d. **Community Empowerment:** Prioritize reaching out to untapped communities lacking energy access, aiming to provide them with renewable energy solutions and contribute to their socioeconomic development.
- e. **Conflict of Interest Avoidance:** Implement strict guidelines and policies to prevent any conflicts of interest between the government, fossil fuel companies, and renewable energy stakeholders, ensuring an unbiased and fair transition process.

3. Implementation Steps:

Step 1: Establish a dedicated task force comprising experts in energy economics, data analysis, renewable energy, and community development.

Step 2: Collaborate with relevant stakeholders, including government agencies, fossil fuel companies, renewable energy providers, and local communities, to gather necessary data and insights.

Step 3: Develop a robust data management system, incorporating rigorous quality control measures and ensuring data security and privacy.

Step 4: Analyse revenue streams from fossil fuel companies, considering taxes, royalties, and other financial contributions to accurately understand the government's earnings.

Step 5: Conduct feasibility studies through a collaboration with the academia and engage renewable energy experts to formulate a comprehensive transition plan, considering factors such as technology options, infrastructure requirements, and policy frameworks.

Step 6: Establish a user-friendly online platform to publish reports, data visualizations, and progress updates for public access. The platform must indicate which areas and providers are doing important efforts based on the composition of their energy mix. This can be showcased using the following transition levels:

- **Level 1: Not yet transitioning** (0% to 19% renewable energy)
- **Level 2: Slowly transitioning** (20% to 39% renewable energy)
- **Level 3: Partially transitioned** (40% to – 59% renewable energy)
- **Level 4: Almost transitioned** (60% to 79% renewable energy)
- **Level 5: Fully transitioned** (80 to 100% renewable energy)

If necessary, the renewable energy source can also be broken down (e.g.: wind, solar, biofuels, etc.). The platform should grow independently encouraging a decentralized sharing of information.

Step 7: Implement renewable energy projects in untapped communities, leveraging public-private partnerships and funding mechanisms to ensure sustainable and inclusive energy access.

Step 8: Create a “Seal of Sustainability” to be awarded to organizations and companies that are “Almost transitioned” and “Fully transitioned” to renewable energy and provides accurate energy data transparency. Metrics should be established together by all stakeholders but can use the existing ESG Metrics (Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics). Here are the examples:

- **Environmental Metrics:** Tracking carbon emissions, capacity of renewable energy, and energy savings and efficiency. According to Quantive, the following should be monitored:
 - Greenhouse gases
 - Air pollution
 - Energy consumption
 - Water consumption
 - Waste output
 - Nature usage
 - Environmental policies
- **Social Metrics:** Locational energy access, generated jobs, and communal participation. We can again consider Quantive’s metrics:
 - Comparative living wages
 - Diversity, equity, and inclusion percentage
 - Gender pay gap
 - Employee engagement
 - Reskilling/training
 - Health and safety
 - Human rights
 - Charity
 - Wealth generation
- **Governance Metrics:** Policy and regulation, good governance audits (especially for procurement and licenses),

and publication and disclosure using international reporting standards like Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) focusing on Sector Standard for Oil and Gas, and Sector Standard for Coal

Step 9: Monitor and evaluate the initiative's impact regularly using data, incorporating feedback from the public, communities, and stakeholders to drive continuous improvement.

Step 10: Encourage active participation from the public through feedback that must be integrated in the platform mentioned in Step 6. The platform should show which providers cover a specific area and what energy source are they using.

4. Key Benefits:

a. Transparency: Enhances public trust by providing transparent information on government earnings and the transition to renewable energy.

b. Accountability: Holds fossil fuel companies and the government accountable for their contributions to the energy sector and the environment.

c. Sustainable Development: Facilitates the transition to renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting socioeconomic development in untapped communities.

d. Innovation and Investment: Attracts investments in renewable energy projects, fostering innovation, job creation, and economic growth.

e. Empowerment: Equips citizens with knowledge to actively participate in energy-related discussions and decision-making processes.

f. Conflict Resolution: Mitigates potential conflicts of interest by ensuring an impartial and fair approach to the transition process.

5. Beneficiaries:

a. Citizens: Residents would be able to understand their provider's obligations and how to switch to renewable energy. Additionally, they will receive open disclosure of information on how the government oversees fossil fuel businesses and receives payments from them as a result.

b. Consumers: Consumers occupy the vast bulk of the current energy grid. They would be able to be more perceptive and conscious of their origins and the processes involved in their production as a result.

c. Environment: The preservation of natural resources and ecosystems has a positive impact on reducing carbon emissions and reducing the effects of climate change. By minimizing the pollution and environmental damage caused by the production, consumption, and extraction of fossil fuels, we can encourage the use of renewable energy sources and lessen our reliance on them.

d. Industries: Sectors with a high reliance on fossil fuels may have a clearer understanding of the potential repercussions of not utilizing renewable energy sources to support their operations. Then, by tweaking their practices in accordance with the initiatives' and projects' findings, they can gradually reduce their carbon footprints.

e. Investors and Financiers: There is a growing trend of ESG compliant investments, and individuals and organizations within the financing industry are flocking in to identify the next green investments. They will benefit from this proposal since they will have access to sustainable investment opportunities in the renewable energy sector, aligning with ESG criteria and supporting their responsible investment strategies. This will also mitigate climate-related financial risks associated with fossil fuel investments.

f. Government and Public Institutions: To increase financial and environmental reporting across numerous sectors of Philippine society, better legislation and laws can be developed. Better projects could result from this, enabling isolated areas to obtain renewable energy. Achieving the national climate change and sustainable development goals can further enhance the country's reputation and international standing as a responsible and environmentally conscious travel destination. The macroeconomic health of the country can be improved by the introduction of better tax laws, employment creation, and investment income.

g. Researchers: As long as this proposal can be implemented with the goal of sustainability and continuity, local and international researchers would have a working prototype of what a developing country would look like if everything are mostly powered by renewable energy.

6. Hypotheses:

Environmental Impact:	
Null	The energy transition strategy won't result in a considerable decrease in the carbon emissions from the energy sector.
Alternative	The energy sector's carbon emissions will be significantly reduced as a result of the energy transition strategy.
Renewable Energy Adoption:	
Null	The implementation of the energy transition plan will not significantly increase the share of renewable energy in the overall energy mix.
Alternative	The percentage of renewable energy in the overall energy mix will rise dramatically when the energy transition plan is put into action.
Energy Efficiency:	
Null	The energy transition strategy won't result in a considerable increase in energy efficiency across all industries.
Alternative	Energy efficiency will significantly increase across all sectors as a result of the energy transition strategy.
Social Impact:	
Null	Access to energy for underserved and vulnerable people will not be considerably improved by the energy transition strategy.
Alternative	The energy transition plan will significantly improve access to energy for underserved and marginalized communities.
Governance and Transparency:	
Null	The governance and openness of the energy sector will not increase as a result of the energy transition strategy.
Alternative	The energy transition strategy will make the industry more transparent and conducive to good governance.
Economic Impact:	
Null	The energy transition strategy won't significantly boost the economy of the renewable energy sector or create new jobs.
Alternative	The energy transition strategy will lead to a large increase in the number of jobs and economic activity in the renewable energy industry.
Stakeholder Engagement:	
Null	Stakeholders will not be adequately involved in decision-making processes or have their concerns addressed by the

	energy transition plan.
Alternative	Involving stakeholders in decision-making processes and addressing their concerns will be accomplished through the energy transition plan.

7. Project Timeline:

ID	Name	Jan, 23		Jan, 24		Jan, 25		Jan, 26		Jan, 27			
		H:	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1
1	Proposal Development and Submission												
2	Project Planning and Resource Allocation												
3	Research and Data Collection												
4	Development of the Energy Transition Plan												
5	Proposal Review and Approval												
6	Implementation and Monitoring												
7	Project Evaluation and Reporting												

I. Proposal Development and Submission:

- Duration: 1 month
- Tasks:
 - Develop project proposal and objectives
 - Conduct stakeholder consultations
 - Finalize proposal document
 - Submit proposal to PH-EITI

II. Project Planning and Resource Allocation:

- Duration: 2 months
- Tasks:
 - Form project team and assign responsibilities
 - Identify and allocate necessary resources (budget, personnel, etc.)
 - Develop a detailed project plan
 - Define project milestones and deliverables

III. Research and Data Collection:

- Duration: 3 months
- Tasks:
 - Conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current energy landscape
 - Collect data on fossil fuel earnings and renewable energy potential
 - Analyze socioeconomic and environmental impacts
 - Identify untapped communities with no access to energy grids

IV. Development of the Energy Transition Plan:

- Duration: 4 months
- Tasks:
 - Formulate the energy transition goals and targets
 - Establish policy and regulatory frameworks
 - Design strategies for renewable energy expansion and energy efficiency
 - Identify infrastructure development needs
 - Define stakeholder engagement and capacity-building initiatives

V. Proposal Review and Approval:

- Duration: 1 month
- Tasks:
 - Submit the developed energy transition plan to PH-EITI for review
 - Address any feedback and revisions required
 - Obtain final approval for the energy transition plan

VI. Implementation and Monitoring:

- Duration: 24 months
- Tasks:

- Execute the energy transition plan, including policy implementation and renewable energy projects
- Monitor and evaluate progress against set targets and milestones
- Conduct regular reporting on ESG metrics and project outcomes
- Engage with stakeholders and address concerns or challenges

VII. Project Evaluation and Reporting:

- Duration: 2 months
- Tasks:
 - Evaluate the overall impact and effectiveness of the energy transition project
 - Analyze the achieved outcomes against the initial objectives
 - Prepare a comprehensive project report
 - Present the findings and recommendations to PH-EITI and the Department of Finance

8. Resources:

Adbheadhonso. "Accelerating the Clean Energy Transition in Southeast Asia." Asian Development Bank, May 24, 2023. <https://www.adb.org/projects/55124-001/main>.

"Data," n.d. <https://www.irena.org/Data>.

"GRI - Sector Standard for Coal," n.d. <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/standards-development/sector-standard-for-coal/>.

"GRI - Sector Standard for Oil and Gas," n.d. <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/standards-development/sector-standard-for-oil-and-gas/>.

"What Are ESG Metrics? Top ESG Metrics to Know | Quantive," n.d. <https://quantive.com/resources/articles/esg-metrics>.

US EPA. "Local Renewable Energy Benefits and Resources | US EPA," March 30, 2023. <https://www.epa.gov/statelocalenergy/local-renewable-energy-benefits-and-resources>.